

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Enhanced Electrochemical Stability for Sodium-ion Capacitors by Introducing Glyoxylic-acetal Based Electrolyte

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Data Evaluation

Galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements were conducted to perform differential capacity analysis. For that purpose, the raw data (potential and capacity) was processed to be monotonous. Then, the data was reduced and the remaining data points were made equidistant.

For determining the (gravimetric) energy density E_g of the SIC devices the product of current and voltage is integrated over the time and divided by the mass (Equation 1). This equation is used for non-ideal EDLCs as well as hybrid systems and was thus chosen for this work.^[1]

$$E_g = \frac{1}{m} \int V(t) I(t) dt \quad (1)$$

The maximum specific power density is obtained by using the same power calculation, hence, the product of voltage and current. Then, the negative maximum of the power of one GCD cycle as depicted in **Fig.S1** is determined. With this technique the power after the IR-drop is determined leading to the maximum power which is actually available.

Figure S1. Determination of the maximum specific power. Through GCPL-measurements the applied current is known and the voltage is detected. By multiplying the two values the power results. The minimum of the power curve equals the maximum releasable power.

Figure S2. Density. Density values recorded between 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the two investigated electrolytes.

Figure S3. Anodic Dissolution. Anodic Dissolution tests of NaTFSI in TEG:PC and NaPF₆ in EC:PC between 2 and 4 V (a). The NaPF₆ in EC:PC electrolyte is able to passivate the Al current collector while for NaTFSI in TEG:PC significant anodic dissolution is occurring. Anodic dissolution test with changed upper cut-off potential to 3.8 V for NaTFSI in TEG:PC (b). By reducing the upper cut-off potential the anodic dissolution is remarkably less distinct for NaTFSI in TEG:PC.

Figure S4. Capacity Balancing. Capacity of HC and AC half-cells with the two investigated electrolytes at a mass ratio of HC 1:1.4 AC.

Table S1. Capacity Balancings at different current densities. The values were obtained by extrapolating the capacity measurements of HC and AC half-cells with the respective electrolytes.

Current Density [mA g ⁻¹]	q(HC)/q(AC)	q(HC)/q(AC)
	NaPF ₆ in EC:PC	NaTFSI in TEG:PC
100	1.89	2.16
200	1.64	1.92
500	1.10	1.23
1000	0.78	0.78

Presodiation

It was shown, that a coulombic efficiency of $> 99\%$ was reached in the half-cell precycling indicating that a stable equilibrium state is reached. For NaTFSI in TEG:PC 271 mA h g^{-1} were stored in the HC electrode and for NaPF_6 in EC:PC 276 mA h g^{-1} . The presodiated HC electrodes were then inserted into a fresh half-cell against Na. In the first discharge capacity values of 240 mA h g^{-1} (NaTFSI in TEG:PC) and 225 mA h g^{-1} (NaPF₆ in EC:PC) were obtained. Resulting in 90% (NaTFSI in TEG:PC) and 81% (NaPF₆ in EC:PC) of coulombic efficiency in between the last discharge of the precycling and the first charge of the new cell. Also, the ICE of precycled HC electrodes are all above 92% indicating a certain stability of the beforehand built-up SEI (compared to 75% ICE in half-cell investigations). With this result, it is also shown that the disassembling of the cell and insertion of the precycled HC into a fresh cell does not significantly influence the stored capacity.

Figure S5. Half-cell with presodiated HC (pHC) against Na metal verifying the success of the presodiation process.

Figure S6. Cell voltage and potentials during float experiments of SICs with NaPF_6 in EC:PC (a) and NaTFSI in TEG:PC (b). For NaPF_6 in EC:PC a significant positive potential drift can be observed.

Figure S7. Float tests of half-cells. Capacity and C.E. for presodiated HC (pHC) half-cell (a) and AC half-cell (b). The pHC was held at 5 mV and the AC at 3.8 V. Both half-cell systems are stable with both electrolytes.

Figure S8. XPS spectra (C1s, O1s and F1s) of pristine and floated AC electrodes. The pristine electrode is depicted in black-gray colors, the electrode floated in a SIC with NaPF₆ in EC:PC in blue shades and the electrode floated in a SIC with NaTFSI in TEG:PC in green shades.

Figure S9. XPS spectra (O1s) of pristine and floated HC electrodes. The pristine electrode is depicted in black-gray colors, the electrode floated in a SIC with NaPF₆ in EC:PC in blue shades and the electrode floated in a SIC with NaTFSI in TEG:PC in green shades.

References

- [1] Y. Zhang, J. Jiang, Y. An, L. Wu, H. Dou, J. Zhang, Y. Zhang, S. Wu, M. Dong, X. Zhang et al., *ChemSusChem* **2020**, *13*, 2522–2539.